

TREATMENT OF VARICOSE VEIN FOR WOMEN

Every woman wants to have nice smooth legs throughout their lives but often falls victim to varicose veins. Varicose [vein treatment memorial](#) is a cosmetic concern and not life-threatening in most cases. Some people complain that the veins cause them pain or discomfort. It is always best to get them looked at to see what type of **varicose vein treatment near me** is available to you for the type of condition you have. In most cases, it will just look bad and not hurt you at all.

Risk factors that cause varicose veins

The development of varicose veins in women will depend on some of these factors :

- **Pregnancy:** The blood volume in your body increases during the time of pregnancy. This change is very helpful for the fetus but it will produce some side effects on your body by enlarging the veins. The Changing of hormones during pregnancy is also an important factor.

- **Age:** The other main factor which causes varicose veins in your body is your increasing age. The wear and tear of vein valves to regulate the blood flow is caused by aging.
- **During Period:** The hormonal changes during the period are certainly a factor in causing varicose veins. At this period, the hormones of females tend to relax vein walls.

- Family history: There are maximum chances of having varicose veins to you if your other family members had.

Varicose vein treatments

Some **varicose vein treatment city center** you might want to consider are:

1. Radiofrequency ablation- This is where a high-frequency electric current brings heat to the dilated veins. This damages them and causes them to close. You need a **vein specialist**, to be put to sleep for the procedure because of the pain factor if you were to be awake for it. After this procedure, you won't have to worry about your varicose veins anymore.

2. Non-surgical:- Such things like compression stockings are good to look into. These stockings relieve the swelling and aching. The stockings help the blood flow in your legs go to your heart. This often stops the varicose veins from forming further but it is not guaranteed. So, you have to seek [vein treatment](#) for a better consultation. This could be what it takes for most people.

3. Surgery- When you have had enough of the pain and discomfort of your dilated veins, surgery is an option you might want to consider. But before going to the surgery you should consider the **vein specialist city center**. The two most common methods in surgery are stripping and ligation. In this procedure, they remove the veins which causes the problem. Being sure to use preventative measures, and you won't have to worry about them returning.

Having any procedure done to you is going to cause you pain and discomfort because of the uneasiness of the task. There could be a chance that your veins are only slight and not have to require any extra work on your part. Be sure to consult **vein treatment near me** when you see the veins forming and get the correct varicose vein treatment you need.